

Effectiveness of Benson's Relaxation Therapy on level of anxiety among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas

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ABSTRACT

Background of the study: Anxiety is increasingly common among nursing students due to academic pressure, clinical exposure, and career uncertainty. Non-pharmacological approaches like Benson's Relaxation Therapy, developed by Herbert Benson, offer a simple, cost-effective method to reduce anxiety without side effects.

Objectives: 1.To assess the level of anxiety among students in selected Nursing colleges. 2.To evaluate the effectiveness of Benson's relaxation therapy on level of anxiety among students studying in Nursing colleges. **Secondary Objectives:** 1.To find association between selected demographic variables i.e. and pretest study finding anxiety among Nursing students.

Research methodology: A Research Methodology adopted for the study. A quantitative research approach was used with a quasi-experimental non-equivalent control group design. The study was conducted among Nursing students aged 18–25 years in selected Nursing colleges. The sample consisted of students divided into an experimental group and a control group using a non-probability sampling technique. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were clearly defined.

Result: Researcher applied paired t-test for the effectiveness of Benson's relaxation therapy on level of anxiety among students studying in Nursing colleges. Paired t-test showed anxiety scores decreased from 20 (pretest) to 13 (post-test) in the experimental group ($t=5$, $df=24$, $p<0.05$), indicating significant effectiveness of Benson's relaxation therapy. In the control group, scores changed from 10 to 8 ($t=1.73$, $df=24$, $p<0.05$), showing a comparatively smaller reduction.

Conclusion : The study concluded that Benson's relaxation technique is effective in reducing anxiety among nursing students. It is a simple, cost-effective complementary therapy that can be easily used by nurses without complications.

Keywords: Anxiety; Bensons relaxation therapy; Relaxation therapy; Nursing students; Mental Health; Experimental study

Introduction: Anxiety is a common psychological condition that affects individuals across all age groups, particularly students who are exposed to continuous academic, clinical, and social pressures. Nursing students are especially vulnerable to anxiety due to the demanding nature of their education, which includes rigorous theoretical learning, clinical responsibilities, patient care exposure, examinations, and performance expectations. Persistent anxiety can negatively influence academic achievement, clinical competence, emotional stability, and overall well being. Therefore, it becomes essential to identify effective, safe, and economical interventions to reduce anxiety among Nursing students. The present study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of Benson's Relaxation Therapy on the level of anxiety among students studying in Nursing colleges of selected areas. The conceptual foundation of the study was based on the General System Theory proposed by Ludwig Von Bertalanffy (1968), which emphasizes input, throughput, output, and feedback processes. In this study, the input referred to the pre-test level of anxiety among Nursing students; throughput referred to the implementation of Benson's Relaxation Therapy; and output referred to the post-test level of anxiety after intervention.

Background of the study

Background and need for the study. Anxiety has become increasingly prevalent among college students worldwide. Academic pressure, fear of failure, clinical exposure, peer comparison, and uncertainty about future career prospects contribute significantly to anxiety levels among Nursing students. While pharmacological interventions are available, they may produce side effects and are not always feasible for students. Non-pharmacological therapies, particularly relaxation techniques, have gained recognition due to their simplicity, cost effectiveness, and absence of adverse effects. Benson's Relaxation Therapy, developed by Dr. Herbert Benson in the 1970s, is a meditative technique designed to elicit the "relaxation response,"

Research methodology

A Research Methodology adopted for the study. A quantitative research approach was used with a quasi-experimental non-equivalent control group design. The study was conducted among Nursing students aged 18–25 years in selected Nursing colleges. The sample consisted of students divided into an experimental group and a control group using a non-probability sampling technique. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were clearly defined. Data were collected using the Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A), a standardized tool used to measure anxiety levels. The experimental group received Benson's Relaxation Therapy for 20 minutes twice daily over a specified period, while the control group did not receive any intervention. Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional ethics committee, and written informed consent was taken from all participants. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained. The data collection process included pre-test assessment of anxiety levels in both groups, administration of the intervention to the experimental group, and post-test assessment for both groups. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to describe demographic variables and anxiety levels. Inferential statistics included the paired t-test to compare pre-test and post-test anxiety scores within groups and Fisher's exact test to determine associations between anxiety levels and demographic variables.

Section I: Description of samples (Nursing students) based on their characteristics.
Demographic data analysis:

Table 1: Description of samples (Nursing students) based on their characteristics in terms of frequency and percentage

(N=E-25, C-25)

SCALE – SCORE					
		Experimental group		Control group	
SR.NO	DEMOGRAPHIC DATA	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1.	Age group				
a.	18-20 years	10	40	13	52
b.	21-25 years	15	60	12	48
2.	Gender				
a.	Male	8	32	10	40
b.	Female	17	68	15	60
3.	Residence				
a.	Rural	13	52	8	32
b.	Urban	12	48	17	68
4.	Socioeconomic status				
a.	Upper class	4	16	5	20
b.	Middle class	10	40	10	40
c.	Lower class	11	44	10	40

SECTION -II To evaluate the effectiveness of Benson’s relaxation therapy on level of anxiety among students studying in Nursing colleges.

(N=E-25, C-25)

FIG NO -1 Bar diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution of samples according to experimental group pretest anxiety level and control group anxiety level among Nursing students

(N=E-25, C-25)

Table 5: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of Benson’s relaxation therapy on level of anxiety among students studying in Nursing colleges.

(N=E-25, C-25)

Experimental group	Mean	SD	T	df	P -value
Pretest	20	4.7	5	24	0.0001
Post test	13	2.8			

(N=E-25, C-25)

Control group	Mean	SD	T	df	P -value
Pretest	10	5	1.73	24	0.0001
Post test	8	6			

Statistical Analysis of Control Group The researcher employed a sample t-test to analyse the effectiveness of the intervention within the control group. The mean stress score observed in the pre-test for the control group was 10, while the post-test mean score reduced to 8. The calculated t-value for this comparison was 1.73 with 24 degrees of freedom. The resulting p-value was found to be less than 0.05, indicating statistical significance.

(N=E-25, C-25)

FIG NO -6 Average score of anxiety level in control group

Section III -To find association between selected demographic variables i.e. and pretest study finding anxiety among Nursing students. Analysis of data related to association of level anxiety with demographic variables Table 10: Fisher's exact test for the association of anxiety with demographic variables

(N=E-25, C-25)

SCALE – SCORE						
SR.NO	DEMOGRAPHIC DATA	<17	18-24	25-30	INFERENCE	P VALUE
1.	Age group					
a.	18-20	0	4	6	No significance	0.566
b.	21-25	0	7	8		
2.	Gender					
a.	Male	0	4	4	No significance	0.57
b.	Female	0	8	9		
3.	Residence					
a.	Rural	0	6	7	No significance	0.677
b.	Urban	0	6	6		
4.	Socioeconomic status					
a.	Upper class	0	1	3	No significance	0.77
b.	Middle class	0	5	5		
c.	Lower class	0	4	7		

DISCUSSION

The present study was undertaken to evaluate the effectiveness of Benson's Relaxation Therapy on the level of anxiety among Nursing students studying in selected colleges. This chapter discusses the major findings of the study in relation to the stated objectives, hypotheses, and relevant literature. Effectiveness of Benson's Relaxation Therapy

RECOMMENDATION

On the basis of the present study, the investigator suggested the following recommendation for further study. A study to assess the effectiveness of Benson's relaxation technique on level of anxiety among Alcoholic patients, school children's different profession can be Conducted.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study revealed that the Benson's relaxation technique was effective on level of anxiety among Nursing students of selected colleges. Thus, study suggest that Benson's relaxation technique is a complimentary alternative therapy that's help the nurse to reduce level of anxiety among various patients, in an easy, cost-effective way without any complications

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SUMMARY

This chapter include analysis and interpretation of data in that study objectives, and hypothesis testing performed by inferential statistics, paired t-test used to find the effectiveness of Benson's relaxation therapy on level of anxiety among students studying in Nursing colleges. it shows that Benson's relaxation therapy is effective to reduce anxiety among students studying in Nursing colleges. fisher exact test used to find association between pretest finding with demographic variables included in this study.

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